

Effect of Reflective Inquiry Instructional Technique on Students' Achievement and Retention in Electronics Works in Technical Colleges in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study determined the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' achievement and retention in electronics works in Technical Colleges in Rivers State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted pre-test post-test non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design. The study was conducted in Rivers State. The population for the study was 87 National Technical Certificate 11 students and it was a census, but purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the two Technical Colleges offering electronics works in Rivers State. The instrument for data collection was a teacher made test titled, Electronics Works Achievement and Retention Test. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts. The reliability was determined using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient and found to be 0.73. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while analysis of covariance was used for testing the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. Findings from the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught principles of radio transmission and electronic circuits with reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same topics with demonstration method. Also, the findings revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught electronics works with reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same subject with demonstration method. From these findings, the study recommended among others that reflective inquiry instructional technique should be used for the teaching of electronics works as this will enhance academic achievements and retention ability of the students.

Keywords: Reflective Inquiry, Instructional Technique, Students' Achievement, Retention, Electronics Works

INTRODUCTION

Education is an instrument for economic advancement. In its technical sense, education is a process by which society deliberately transmits knowledge, practical skills and values from one generation to another. Smith (2020) stated that educational programmes are instruments that can be used in solving societal problems, bring desirable changes in the people by equipping them with skills and knowledge needed for self-reliance as well as sustainable development. The societal problems such as increased population, civilization, poverty, unemployment among others are due to lack of employable skills and other related factors that can be addressed through educational programmes such as technical, vocational education and training (TVET) (Smart, 2015).

Technical Vocational Education and Training has been adopted by many nations as that educational programme that provides training for paid or self-employment with a view to enabling the transition from secondary education to work for young trainees/students (social objective) and supply the labour market with competent

apprentices (economic objective) (Imani & Bodo 2021). Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2013) defined TVET as a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life.

Achievement of TVET objectives are important functions of formal vocational and technical education institutions in Nigeria such as Polytechnics, Technical Colleges among others. Technical Colleges give vocational training to prepare students for entry into specific engineering trades by offering several subjects/trades that prepare them for employment after graduation, among such subjects/trades are electrical installation works and electronics works (Robinson, 2020). Robinson continued that electronics works is a technological subject that involves the application of scientific theories and principles in the design, production, installation, testing, servicing, use, and

control of electrical and electronic parts, equipment and systems. Electronic technicians normally work as members of engineering teams in applied design, product development, installation, maintenance, manufacturing, production, or telecommunications among others (Olsen, 2013).

Electronic works in technical colleges according to National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) Syllabus (2022) consists of three sections or units which are used for the assessment of students' academic achievement, and they are; Electronic devices and circuit, Radio communication and Television. Electronic devices and circuits deal with the design and applications of semiconductor components such as diodes, triodes, transistors, rectifiers, oscillators among others (Olsen, 2013). Continuing, Olsen, described electric circuit to be a closed path of wires and electrical components which allows current to flow through it on the application of potential difference between two points in the path. The purpose of circuits is to get electricity and its considerable energy potential exactly where it needs to go and to contain the potential harmful effects of electricity in the process. An electronic circuit can usually be categorized as an analog circuit, a digital circuit, or a mixed-signal circuit (a combination of analog circuits and digital circuits) (Pizzi & Jones, 2014). The knowledge of electronics devices and circuits as well as practical skills are necessary for diagnosing and carrying out repairs on radio communication gadgets and televisions.

Radio receiver also known as a receiver or simply a radio is an electronic device that receives signal in the form of radio waves and converts the signal to a usable form. In Technical Colleges, the most familiar type of radio receiver is a broadcast radio receiver commonly called radio which reproduces sound transmitted by radio broadcasting stations (Pizzi & Jones, 2014). However, principles of radio receivers are widely used in other areas of modern technology, such as television transmission and reception among others (Idris, Saba & Mustapha, 2014). The aspect of communication involving the transmission of both vision and sound is referred to as television (TV) broadcasting. It is one thing to teach electronics works in Technical Colleges using an appropriate teaching method and teaching aids but another for the learners to retain and remember what they have been taught after the elapsing of some reasonable

period of time, which is retention (Ajai, 2012). Retention is the process of keeping knowledge over time or the ability of an organism to store, retain, and recall information. Retention of knowledge is the ability of an individual to reproduce valuable knowledge after a period of time. This implies that any pedagogical strategy adopted to improve achievement should be able to improve students' retentive ability in the subject. Retention in electronic works is not acquired by mere memorization but through appropriate teaching approach.

Onose as cited in (Ajai, 2012) stated that the teaching and learning requires the discovery of innovations that will promote knowledge retention, which in turn enhances students' academic achievement. Academic Achievement according to Horrocks and Schoovner as cited in (Asuru, 2015), is used to indicate the degree of success attained in some general or specific area within the school context. Academic achievement indicates the extent to which the student, teacher, curricular and indeed the educational institution have achieved the predetermined educational goals. Academic achievement is commonly measured using examinations that assess important procedural knowledge such as skills, and declarative knowledge such as facts which student have learnt (Asuru, 2015). Asuru continued that academic achievement of students therefore must be viewed from those three educational domains. Cognitive domain refers to knowledge therefore, the cognitive domain includes all objectives that relates to recall of knowledge, the development of mental and intellectual abilities. Students achievement in cognitive domain in a school subject is usually designated by a score or mark obtained in an achievement test (Yahaya, Chado & Eviti, 2021). Test according to Olaitan (in Bargu, 2013) is an instrument administered to an individual as a stimulus to elicit certain desired and expected response as demanded in the instrument. Asuru (2015) defined achievement test as an attainment test designed to appraise or measure what the student has learned to do as a result of planned previous experience or training often provided in schools. It is used to find out the extent to which a testee has achieved, gained, or mastered certain information or skill after he/she has been exposed to some instruction or training in the aforesaid area. Achievement test may be teacher made or standardized test.

However, psychomotor achievement refers to achievement in psychomotor task in a school subject as designated by a score or mark in an achievement or performance test. Okoro (in Bargu, 2013) explained that performance test involves the use of tools and equipment in a direct assessment of the amount of practical skills possessed by the student. Students' cognitive and psychomotor achievements in a course depends on several factors among which include learning environment and instructional method. One of the most overbearing factors is the effect teaching method has on the students' academic achievement. Asuru (2015) stated that students' academic achievement is dwindling partly due to inadequate teaching methods employed by the teachers. This could be the cause of the widening gap between the skills students acquired in schools and the skills needed to succeed in the increasing global, technological infused 21st century workplace.

Poor instructional techniques such as the teacher-centered methods are considered obsolete, a big burden with little impact on students' development. There are hues and cries that some teachers at various levels of education are accustomed to traditional methods of teaching such as lecture, demonstration, didactic teaching methods among others. The traditional methods of teaching do not adequately cater for the diverse learning styles of Technical College students and this has barred the students from acquiring higher order thinking skills for adaptability (Maonga, 2015).

Electronic works syllabus requires teaching strategies that will enhance the students' active participation in the teaching and learning processes inside and outside the classroom. As a student-centered programme, students' active participation at every stage of the instruction is required. In view of the general objectives of electronic works, it can be argued that electronics works teaching in Technical Colleges should have changed in terms of teaching methods and techniques (Maonga, 2015). Hence the need to switch to a learner centered method of teaching such as active learning techniques which include; experiential learning technique, inquiry based learning, problem based learning, reflective inquiry technique among others (Olitoquit, 2014).

However, it is notable that any educational venture or programme that creates room for students to observe, ask

questions, and actively participate in the teaching and learning process is under the umbrella of reflective inquiry instructional technique (Anyima, as cited in Ezeudu, Olaowei, & Umeifekwem, 2014). Reflective inquiry is a broad based instructional technique that affords learners the opportunity to think critically, discuss and share their wealth of knowledge and experiences (both past and present) together in small groups on a particular subject matter (Anyima, as cited in Ezeudu, Olaowei, & Umeifekwem, 2014).

Reflective inquiry instructional technique according to Mason (2012) is an innovative trend that incorporates a blend of scaffolded learning, inquiry and critical thinking skills, questioning skills, discussion, and collaborative learning in order to promote effective teaching and learning. It is therefore seen not as a one-way technique. Reflective inquiry is learner centered as it engages learners in series of questioning and thinking processes which makes learners construct knowledge within and among themselves without necessarily relying on the teacher for everything (Ogbuanya & Owodunni, 2013). Reflective inquiry according to Eastern Mennonite University [EMU], (2013) is seen as a continuous teaching/learning processes that encourages life-long learning which motivates and sustains students' interests in learning and as well facilitates long time retention and transfer of learning in real life situation. Teaching students using reflective teaching strategies helps them develop higher-order thinking skills needed for technological development.

The rapid rate of technological development in the electronic world of work calls for a change in the instructional delivery system used in training electronic works craftsmen in Technical Colleges. This is owing to the fact that the present instructional delivery system which include demonstration teaching method, lecture method among others maybe the reason the students recorded poor academic achievement in electronics works at public examinations such as West African Examination Council WAEC and NABTEB and at the work place when employed (Fawcet in Ogbuanya & Owodunni, 2013).

Robinson (2020) maintained that when traditional method of teaching is employed, students' ability to grasp relevant concepts is made much more difficult than when students are exposed to lessons involving hands-

on experience in school. Against this background, it can be argued that students' academic achievement and retention in electronic works can be improved if a student-centred teaching method is employed. This underscores the background to which this study was undertaken to determine the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' academic achievement and retention in electronic works in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Technical Colleges are established to provide training and impart necessary skills to students for self-reliance or employment in the world of work (FRN, 2013). But in spite of the huge government investments in Technical Colleges, it is observed that technical education programmes do not seem to adequately achieve the objectives as majority of graduates from Technical Colleges are unemployed and in addition, training acquired in Technical Colleges seems inadequate to make electronics works graduates competent and self-reliant as emphasized by the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013). However, it is also observed by Robinson (2020) that there is an incessant poor academic achievement and low retention of knowledge by students of electronic works who have completed their modules in annual national examination conducted by NABTEB. Robinson continued that the report from NABTEB's chief examiner revealed that electronics works students have been recording high failure rates for many consecutive years for example, National Technical Certificate and National Business Certificate examinations conducted by NABTEB from May/June 2015-2020 recorded average failure rates of about 60 percent in electronics works.

Also report has shown that electronics works graduates do not have full knowledge and experience of what they claim to have studied, as most of them find it challenging to practice what they have learnt as this could be majorly attributed to the type of instructional technique adopted by the teachers of electronic works. This was corroborated by Aina in (Ogbuanya & Owodunni, 2015) that the persistent poor academic achievement and low retention of knowledge by students in Technical Colleges could be as a result of the use of traditional teaching methods by the teachers. However, it can be argued that students' academic achievement and retention ability in electronic works may be improved if

there is a paradigm shift in the instructional delivery system from teacher centred method of teaching to students' centred method of teaching. Therefore, in order to seek for a better alternative instructional method for the teaching and learning of electronic works, this study investigated the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' achievement and retention in electronic works in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' academic achievement and retention in electronic works in Technical Colleges in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the effect of;

1. reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' academic achievement in principles of radio transmission in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.
2. reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' academic achievement in electronic circuit in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.
3. reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' retention ability in electronic works in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Research Questions

Three research questions guided the study:

1. What is the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' academic achievement in principles of radio transmission in Technical Colleges in Rivers State?
2. What is the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' academic achievement in electronic circuit in Technical Colleges in Rivers State?
3. What is the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' retention ability in electronic works in Technical Colleges in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught principles of radio transmission using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same topic using demonstration method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught electronic circuit using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same topic using demonstration method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught electronic works using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same subject using demonstration method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Materials and Methods

The pre-test, post-test, nonequivalent control group quasi-experimental design was adopted for this study. According to Thomas (2020), quasi-experimental design can be used when it is not possible for the researcher to randomly sample the subject and assign them to treatment groups without disrupting the academic programmes of the schools involved in the study. When participants are not randomly assigned to conditions, however, the resulting groups are likely to be dissimilar in some ways. For this reason, researchers consider them to be nonequivalent. A non-equivalent control group according to Quizlet (2019) is a control group that is matched upon certain preexisting characteristics similar to those observed in a treatment group but to which participants are not randomly assigned. In the pretest posttest nonequivalent control group design there is a treatment group that is given a pretest, receives a treatment (using reflective inquiry instructional technique in teaching them), and then is given a posttest. But at the same time there is a nonequivalent control group that is given a pretest, does not receive the treatment (using reflective inquiry instructional technique in teaching them instead demonstration teaching method was used), and then is given a posttest.

Therefore, this design was considered suitable for this study because intact classes (non-randomized groups) were assigned to the two different. The study was conducted in Rivers State of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 87 National Technical Certificate (NTC) 11 students in the Department of Electronic works trade in the two Technical Colleges in Rivers State. The NTC 11 students were used because they have been exposed to the technical courses including electronics and have chosen electronics as their area of interest. The population was a census, but purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the two Technical Colleges which include Government Technical College Port Harcourt with 32 NTC 11^A students and 29 NTC 11^B students, Federal Science and Technical College Ahoada with 14 NTC11^A students and 12 NTC 11^B students respectively. Four intact classes were used from the two selected Technical Colleges for the study, in such that Government Federal Science and Technical College Ahoada and Government Technical College GTC Port-Harcourt were used for both experimental and control group respectively. The total sample was 87 National Technical Certificate (NTC) 11 students in the Department of Electronic works trade in the two Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

The instrument for the study was a teacher made test. The teacher developed a test instrument titled Electronic Works Achievement and Retention Test (EWART). The Electronic Works Achievement and Retention Test (EWART) was a 40 multiple choice item test. Each has four options. The instrument covered the content areas of the topics selected for the study. Measures were taken to ensure that the necessary psychometric properties were well established. In addition to the main instrument of the study, the researcher wrote two sets of lesson plan for teaching the units set out for the study. Reflective inquiry instructional technique lesson plans were used for the experimental group while Demonstration teaching method lesson plans were used for the control group.

The validation of the instruments took the form of face and content validation. Three experts validated the instruments. The items were therefore reorganized at the end of the face validation. To ensure the content validity, a table of specification on the instrument which ensured an appropriate distribution of the test items, with respect to the relevant content area chosen as well as the

cognitive objective levels desired was applied based on the Bloom’s Taxonomy of education objectives.

To establish the reliability of the instrument, Electronic Works Achievement and Retention Test (EWART) was pilot tested on Electronic Works National Technical Certificate (NTC) 11 students of Government Technical College, Aba in Abia State using test re-test reliability method on randomly sampled population of 40 students in the pilot tested school. The test re-test was carried out within an interval of two weeks and the reliability was determined using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and found to be 0.73. Nunnally as cited by (Okwelle & Ayonmike, 2014) stated that a reliability coefficient of 0.70 is considered a good reliability. Hence the reliability coefficient obtained for this study is higher than 0.70, the instrument is therefore considered good for the study.

The scores generated from the pre-test and post-test administered to the students were used as the data collected for the research. The post test was administered twice within an interval of three weeks immediately after the experiment and revision to generate data for the retention ability of the students. Before the treatment, the pre-test was first administered to the two groups in the first week. The experiment followed for five weeks. After the treatment, the seventh week was used for revision after which a post-test was administered to the two groups.

On the tenth week another post-test was administered to the two groups to determine the retention ability of the students. The same questions used for the pre-test were as well used for the post-tests for the two groups, but the questions were re-arranged. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used for testing the null hypotheses whereby the pretest scores on the students’ achievement served as covariates to the post-test scores at 0.05 level of significance. What justifies the use of Analysis of Covariance in this study is the fact that ANCOVA helps to establish if there is any significant changes in the dependent variable due to the treatment of the independent variable. For testing null hypotheses, if the calculated F-value is equal to or greater than the F-Table value at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypotheses should be rejected. If the p-value is less than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypotheses should be rejected, otherwise accept.

RESULTS

In this study, the analyses of data in relation to the research question and hypotheses are presented in Tables 1- 6

Research Questions 1: What is the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students’ academic achievement in principles of radio transmission in Technical Colleges in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Effect of Reflective Inquiry Instructional Technique on Students’ Academic Achievement in Principles of Radio Transmission

Groups	N	Pre-Test Mean (M_1)	Pre-Test SD ₁	Post-Test Mean (M_2)	Post-Test SD ₂	Mean Difference (Within)	Mean Gain -
Experimental	46	18.413	6.8503	48.522	18.5220	30.109	
Control	41	17.969	6.7296	46.184	16.6401	28.215	1.894
Mean Difference (Between)	87	0.444	0.1207	2.338	1.8819		

Source: *Researcher’s Field Result, 2024* (Note: N = Sample Size)

The result from Table 1 revealed that the experimental group (NTC 11A) with a class size of 46 students from the two Technical Colleges had a pre-test mean (M_1) scores of 18.413 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 48.522 with standard deviations of 6.8503 and 18.5220 respectively. This gives a mean difference (within) of 30.109. Also, the control group (NTC 11B) with a class

size of 41 students from the two Technical Colleges has a pre-test mean (M_1) scores of 17.969 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 46.184 with standard deviations of 6.7296 and 16.6401. This gives a mean difference (within) of 28.215. This implies that the experimental group performed better than the control group at the pre-test stage with a mean difference of 0.444 and standard

deviation of 0.1207. On the other hand, the experimental group also performed better than the control group at the post-test level with a mean difference of 2.338 with standard deviation of 1.8819. The answer to research question 1 is that students taught principle of radio transmission using reflective inquiry instructional technique had mean scores of 48.522 and a mean gain of 30.109 as compared to students taught principle of radio transmission with demonstration method that had mean score of 46.184 and a mean gain of 28.215. This means

that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The mean gain difference was 1.894 in favour of experimental group (NTC 11A) and hence the reflective inquiry instructional technique was effective.

Research Questions 2: What is the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' academic achievement in electronic circuit in Technical Colleges in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Effect of Reflective Inquiry Instructional Technique on Students' Academic Achievement in Electronic Circuit

Groups	N	Pre-Test Mean (M_1)	Pre-Test SD ₁	Post-Test Mean (M_2)	Post-Test SD ₂	Mean Difference (Within)	Mean-Gain
Experimental	46	19.043	6.6695	52.967	18.2567	33.924	10.628
Control	41	17.000	6.4696	40.296	14.3399	23.296	
Mean Difference (Between)	87	2.043	0.1999	12.671	3.9168		

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024* (Note: N = Sample Size)

The result from Table 2 revealed that the experimental group (NTC 11A) with a class size of 46 students from the two Technical Colleges had a pre-test mean (M_1) scores of 19.043 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 52.967 with standard deviations of 6.6695 and 18.2567 respectively. This gives a mean difference (within) of 33.924. Also, the control group (NTC 11B) with a class size of 41 students from the two Technical Colleges has a pre-test mean (M_1) scores of 17.000 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 40.296 with standard deviations of 6.4696 and 14.3399. This gives a mean difference (within) of 23.296. This implies that the control group performed better than the experimental group at the pre-test stage with a mean difference of 2.043 and standard deviation of 0.1999. On the other hand, the experimental group also performed better than the control group at the post-test level with a mean difference of 12.671 with

standard deviation of 3.9168. The answer to research question 2 is that students taught electronic circuit using reflective inquiry instructional technique had mean scores of 52.967 and a mean gain of 33.924 as compared to students taught electronic circuit with demonstration method that had mean score of 40.296 and a mean gain of 23.296. This means that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The mean gain difference was 10.628 in favour of experimental group (NTC 11A) and hence the reflective inquiry instructional technique was effective.

Research Questions 3: What is the effect of reflective inquiry instructional technique on students' retention ability in electronics works in Technical Colleges in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Effect of Reflective Inquiry Instructional Technique on Students' Retention Ability in Electronic Works

Groups	N	Pre-Test Mean (M_1)	Pre-Test SD ₁	Post-Test Mean (M_2)	Post-Test SD ₂	Mean Difference (Within)	Mean-Gain
Experimental	46	20.146	5.7013	50.330	14.213	30.184	4.979
Control	41	16.103	5.3206	41.308	11.014	25.205	
Mean Difference (Between)	87	4.043	0.1999	9.022	3.199		

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024* (Note: N = Sample Size)

The result from Table 3. revealed that the experimental group (NTC 11A) with a class size of 46 students from the two Technical Colleges had a pre-test mean (M_1)

scores of 20.146 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 50.330 with standard deviations of 5.7013 and 14.213 respectively. This gives a mean difference (within) of

30.184. Also, the control group (NTC 11B) with a class size of 41 students from the two Technical Colleges has a pre-test mean (M_1) scores of 16.103 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 41.308 with standard deviations of 5.3206 and 11.014. This gives a mean difference (within) of 25.205. This implies that the experimental group performed better than the control group at the pre-test stage with a mean difference of 4.043 and standard deviation of 0.1999. On the other hand, the experimental group also performed better than the control group at the post-test level with a mean difference of 9.022 with standard deviation of 3.199. The answer to research question 3 is that students taught electronic works using reflective inquiry instructional technique has a higher retention ability with a mean score of 50.330 and a mean gain of 30.184 as compared to students taught electronics

works with demonstration method that had mean score of 41.308 and a mean gain of 25.205. This means that the experimental group retained knowledge better than the control group. The mean gain difference was 4.979 in favour of experimental group (NTC 11A) and hence the reflective inquiry instructional technique was effective.

Testing of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught principles of radio transmission using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same topic using demonstration method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Table 4: The Analysis of Covariance Table Showing the Mean Achievement of Students taught Principle of Radio Transmission Using Reflective Inquiry Instructional Technique and those taught same topic with Demonstration Method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1724.215 ^a	2	862.108	8.162	.00
Intercept	1765.172	1	1765.172	16.732	.000
VAR00009	10.255	1	10.255	.097	.756
VAR00007	1005.317	1	1005.317	8.529	.00
Error	10233.345	46	105.498		
Total	62044.000	87			
Corrected Total	11957.560	87			

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024*

From Table 4, F-cal is 8.53 while the p-value is .00 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .00 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significance difference between the mean scores of students taught principle of radio transmission using

reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same topic using demonstration teaching method.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught electronic circuit using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same topic using demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Table 5: The Analysis of Covariance Table Showing the Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Electronic Circuit Using Reflective Inquiry Instructional Technique and those taught same topic using Demonstration teaching Method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	604.457 ^a	2	302.229	2.918	.059
Intercept	1571.328	1	1571.328	15.170	.000
VAR00003	75.457	1	75.457	.728	.395
VAR00001	602.752	1	602.752	5.819	.018
Error	10047.503	46	103.583		
Total	73252.000	87			
Corrected Total	10651.960	87			

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024

From Table 5, F-cal is 5.82 while the p-value is .02 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .02 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught electronic circuit using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those

taught same topic using demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught electronics works using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same subject using demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Table 6: The Analysis of Covariance Table Showing the Mean Retention Scores of Students taught Electronics Works Using Reflective Inquiry Instructional Technique and those taught same subject using Demonstration teaching Method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1437.944 ^a	2	718.972	7.792	.001
Intercept	908.644	1	908.644	9.847	.002
VAR00003	226.904	1	226.904	2.459	.120
VAR00001	1392.973	1	1392.973	15.096	.000
Error	8950.696	46	92.275		
Total	60744.000	87			
Corrected Total	10388.640	87			

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024

From Table 6, F-cal is 15.10 while the p-value is .00 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .00 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significance difference between the mean retention scores of students taught electronics works using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same subject using demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis of the results on Table1 revealed that the experimental group has a pre-test mean scores of 18.413 and a post-test mean scores of 48.522 with standard

deviations of 6.8503 and 18.5220 respectively. This gives a mean difference (within) of 30.109. Also, the control group had a pre-test mean scores of 17.969 and a post-test mean scores of 46.184 with standard deviations of 6.7296 and 16.6401. This gives a mean difference (within) of 28.215. This implies that the experimental group performed better than the control group at the pre-test stage with a mean difference of 0.444 and standard deviation of 0.1207. On the other hand, the experimental group also performed better than the control group at the post-test level with a mean difference of 2.338 with standard deviation of 1.8819. The answer to research question 1 is that students taught principle of radio

transmission using reflective inquiry instructional technique had mean scores of 48.522 and a mean gain of 30.109 as compared to students taught principle of radio transmission with demonstration teaching method that had mean score of 46.184 and a mean gain of 28.215. This means that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The mean gain difference was 1.894 in favour of experimental group and hence the reflective inquiry instructional technique was effective.

The analysis of covariance showed on Table 4, revealed that F-cal is 8.53 while the p-value is .00 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .00 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, the study found a statistically significance difference between the mean scores of students taught principle of radio transmission using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same topic using demonstration teaching method. These findings are in line with Ezeudu, Olaowei and Umeifekwem (2014) who were of the opinion that reflective inquiry instructional technique was significantly more efficacious in improving students' achievement and interest than the traditional demonstration method. In support of the above assertions, Azowenunebi, Adeyemo & Babajide (2019) reported that reflective inquiry enables the learner to reflect on what has been taught and thereby create solvable problems from the lesson which form a guide to the learner and a basis for inquiry into the unknown. In the same vein, Ogbuanya and Owodunni (2015) concluded that reflective inquiry instructional technique is a learner centered method that significantly improves students' academic achievement in electronics works trade.

The analysis of the results on Table 2 revealed that the experimental group with a class size of 46 students from the two Technical Colleges had a pre-test mean (M_1) scores of 19.043 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 52.967 with standard deviations of 6.6695 and 18.2567 respectively. This gives a mean difference (within) of 33.924. Also, the control group with a class size of 41 students from the two Technical Colleges has a pre-test mean (M_1) scores of 17.000 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 40.296 with standard deviations of 6.4696 and 14.3399. This gives a mean difference (within) of 23.296. This implies that the control group performed better than the experimental group at the pre-test stage

with a mean difference of 2.043 and standard deviation of 0.1999. On the other hand, the experimental group also performed better than the control group at the post-test level with a mean difference of 12.671 with standard deviation of 3.9168. The answer to research question 2 is that students taught electronic circuit using reflective inquiry instructional technique had mean scores of 52.967 and a mean gain of 33.924 as compared to students taught electronic circuit with demonstration method that had mean score of 40.296 and a mean gain of 23.296. This means that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The mean gain difference was 10.628 in favour of experimental group and hence the reflective inquiry instructional technique was effective.

The analysis of covariance shown on Table 5, revealed that F-cal is 5.82 while the p-value is .02 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .02 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught electronic circuit with reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same topic with demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State. In line with this finding, Azowenunebi, Adeyemo and Babajide (2019) were of the opinion that students who were exposed to reflective inquiry instructional strategy performed significantly better than those who were not exposed to it. The findings of this study was also in consonant with that of Maonga (2015) who observed that there is a significant difference in learners' performance between students who were taught using reflective inquiry-based teaching method and those taught using traditional methods of teaching in public secondary schools in Kenya. Maonga continued that this implies that public secondary school students are likely to perform better in science and vocational subjects when taught using reflective inquiry-based method in addition to the traditional methods of teaching.

The analysis of the results on Table 3 revealed that the experimental group (NTC 11A) with a class size of 46 students from the two Technical Colleges had a pre-test mean (M_1) scores of 20.146 and a post-test mean (M_2) scores of 50.330 with standard deviations of 5.7013 and 14.213 respectively. This gives a mean difference (within) of 30.184. Also, the control group (NTC11B) with a class size of 41 students from the two Technical

Colleges has a pre-test mean (M1) scores of 16.103 and a post-test mean (M2) scores of 41.308 with standard deviations of 5.3206 and 11.014. This gives a mean difference (within) of 25.205. This implies that the experimental group performed better than the control group at the pre-test stage with a mean difference of 4.043 and standard deviation of 0.1999. On the other hand, the experimental group also performed better than the control group at the post-test level with a mean difference of 9.022 with standard deviation of 3.199. The answer to research question 3 is that students taught electronic works using reflective inquiry instructional technique had a higher retention ability with a mean score of 50.330 and a mean gain of 30.184 as compared to students taught electronic work with demonstration teaching method that had mean score of 41.308 and a mean gain of 25.205. This means that the experimental group retained knowledge better than the control group. The mean gain difference was 4.979 in favour of experimental group and hence the reflective inquiry instructional technique was effective.

The analysis of covariance as shown on Table 6, revealed that F-cal is 15.10 while the p-value is .00 at .05 level of significance. This result shows that p-value of .00 is less than .05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significance difference between the mean retention scores of students taught electronics works using reflective inquiry instructional technique and those taught same subject using demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Rivers State. The findings of this study is in consonant with that of Moses (2020) who opined that using reflective inquiry teaching method to teach students of electrical installation and maintenance works trade enhances the students' retention ability which is visible in the retention test scores. Moses continued that reflective inquiry instructional technique enhances higher retention level in students (both male and female) when used in teaching domestic installation as against the conventional teaching method. This finding is also in tandem with Hassan (2010) who found out that reflective inquiry teaching method enhances students' performance as the students are engaged in critical thinking and thought provoking questions it will lead to their proper understanding and retention of the content of the lesson. Mbah (2012) and Awodun, (2020 in their separate studies also found out that there was significant difference between retention mean scores of students

taught Bricklaying using reflective inquiry instructional technique and conventional lecture method.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings from the research it was concluded that students taught principles of radio transmission and electronic circuits with reflective inquiry instructional technique have higher academic achievement or performed better than those taught same topics with demonstration teaching method. The study also concluded that students taught electronic works with reflective inquiry instructional technique retain what they have learnt more than those taught same subject using demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges. Therefore, reflective inquiry instructional technique is more effective in teaching electronic works in Technical Colleges when compared with demonstration method of teaching.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers of electronic works should adopt reflective inquiry instructional technique in the teaching of electronics works as this will help improve the academic achievements and retention ability of the students.
2. National Board for Technical Education should consider reviewing the curriculum of electronic works with a view to incorporating reflective inquiry instructional technique to enable students learn more effectively.
3. Government should give greater emphasis to in-service education for electronic works teachers to include reflective inquiry instructional technique as this will help improve their knowledge and skills to make them more competent in preparing the 21st century students.

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